

Supplementary information: Pyrolytic carbon microlattices from 3D-printed PEGDA and their in vitro assessment for bone regeneration

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Legends for Supporting Movies:

M1: Z-stack confocal reconstruction of MC3T3-E1 cells cultured on C500 pyrolytic carbon scaffolds.

M2: Z-stack confocal reconstruction of MC3T3-E1 cells on C700 pyrolytic carbon scaffolds.

M3: Z-stack confocal reconstruction of MC3T3-E1 cells cultured on C900 pyrolytic carbon scaffolds.

Supporting Figures:

Figure S1: SEM images of 3D printed PEGDA octet lattices at different magnifications, with the high-magnification images revealing a wrinkly surface topography.

Figure S2: (a) Intensity ratio of D and G peak (I_D/I_G) of the Raman spectra of pyrolyzed PEGDA at different temperatures. Curve-fittings and peak assignment of the Raman spectra of PyC materials pyrolyzed at (b) 410°C, (c) 600°C, (d) 700°C, and (e) 800°C.

Figure S3: Amount of different oxygen-containing functional groups present in PyC samples treated at different pyrolysis temperatures, obtained from the deconvolution of the corresponding O1s spectra, as shown in Figure 2f.

Figure S4: (a) Load-displacement curve of PyC materials at different pyrolysis temperatures obtained in nanoindentation tests. (b) Indentation depth of PyC materials as a function of pyrolysis temperature.

Figure S5: (a) Representative stress-strain curves of PyC octet lattice structures obtained at different pyrolysis temperatures. (b) Magnified stress-strain curve of the PyC samples to emphasize the mechanical responses of C410, C500, and C600. It also shows the slope of each of the curves, depicting the elastic modulus values of the PyC samples.

Figure S6: Variation of the structural density of PyC octet lattices with pyrolysis temperature.

Figure S7: Stretched morphology of MC3T3-E1 cells on PyC scaffolds. The nucleus and cytoskeleton of the cell were stained with DAPI (blue) and Phalloidin (red), respectively, for confocal laser scanning microscopy.

Figure S8: MC3T3-E1 cells connecting multiple lattice elements through extended filopodia on scaffolds (a) C500, (b) C700, and (c) C900.

Figure S9: (a,b) Prominent filopodial spreading of MC3T3-E1 cells on the surfaces of PyC lattices pyrolyzed at 900°C.

Figure S10: Gene expressions of key osteogenic markers, *i.e.*, ALP, Runx2, OCN, and Col1A1, for the control samples, cultured on a culture plate without any scaffold.